

University Brunei Darussalam

Bachelor of Business and Economics

BB-2208 Human Resource Management

Topic: Case Study Analysis

Chosen company:

Ayesha's Farm

Reg. Number: 19b1072

Lecturer: Pg. Dr. Siti Rozaidah Bte Pg. Hj Idris

Submission: 11 November 2020

Table of Contents

1. ABSTRACT.....	1
2. PROBLEM STATEMENT.....	2
3. CASE ANALYSIS.....	4
3.1 HRM Practices.....	6
3.1.1 Hiring.....	6
3.1.2 <i>Training</i>	6
3.1.3 Relations.....	7
3.2 HR Outcomes.....	7
3.2.1 <i>Commitment</i>	7
3.3 Behavioral Outcome.....	8
3.3.1 <i>Motivation</i>	8
3.4 Performance Outcome.....	8
3.4.1 <i>Innovation</i>	8
4. ALTERNATIVE SOLUTION.....	10
4.1 Hiring.....	10
4.2 Training.....	11
5. RECOMMENDATION.....	12
REFERENCES.....	13

1. ABSTRACT

The purpose of this case analysis is to recommend solutions to encounter the problems faced by Ayesha's Farm. This report contains problems that are related to not able to meet the demands of the customer. Other than that, this report also mentioned the problems of commitment or time constraint, finance and limited space. The recommendation given to counter this problem is to hire new employees is concluded as the most suitable solution in order to improve Ayesha's Farm.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Ayesha's Farm is a local business that officially starts operating in 2017. It is owned by Aedy a banker and his wife, Wizana that works as a teacher. Their business is selling hydroponics sets and most of the farming are done by the both of them from the seeding to harvesting. As both of the owners have a fulltime job the business is done on a part-time basis (Musa et al., 2020) .

The first problem is that as their local business is still small, Ayesha's Farm was unable to distribute their product to other shops because they are unsure if they can cater to the demand of their customer as the only employee in their business is themselves. Therefore, if there were a large demand or orders on the hydroponics sets both Aedy and Wizana will not be able to catch up as they do not have enough workers to cater all of the orders that are coming in. By not having enough workers, it would take a longer time to finish one harvest and maintaining their customer hydroponic sets.

Secondly, the commitment given by both Aedy and Wizana is not fully into the business, seeing that Aedy can only focus fully after he arrives home at around 6 to 7 or in the weekends and Wizana with her own responsibility as a teacher. By not giving full attention into the business they may overlook the problems that may arise unexpectedly such as a system failure that leads to an unsuccessful harvest. The actual problem that contributes to the issues are they do not have someone who could give full attention to the business.

Thirdly, is the finance problem, it is where both Aedy and Wizana have to pay their asset such as equipment for the hydroponic and even their bills on water and electricity as it is essential for the

business to continue its operations. As they are still a small business, they do not have a large profit to cover the high expenses and this why the finance problem arise.

Lastly, is the limited space for the Hydroponic farms as the only available space for their farm is at their backyard and this may be due to not having enough capital to afford a larger space for the hydroponic sets. Having a limited space will have an impact on the business and one of the impact is producing lesser harvest. By having lesser harvest they will have lesser profit.

3. CASE ANALYSIS

In 1987, David Guest proposed the Guest Model. It is said that this model is a fusion of aspects that it resembles both Human Resource Management hard and soft approach. In addition, the Guest Model differs from the rest of the Human Resource Management model because, unlike other types of Human Resource Management that rely more on individual growth and management, it puts more emphasis on strategic management.

Guest offers 4 major components that underpin Organizational performance and those components are Strategic Integration, Flexibility, High Commitment and Quality (Thierry, 2018). Firstly, the Strategic Integration is the harder side of the Guest Model, seeing as human resources are handled equally to every other capital with the primary purpose of meeting the business goals. Secondly, Flexibility is when the company and its employees are fundamentally concerned with the need to respond to the evolving market and work environment and the capacity to handle creativity. It holds both hard and soft HRM. Thirdly, High Commitment concerned with the need for both interpersonal dedication, which is the desire to go an extra mile and attitudinal commitment, which is demonstrated by a strong identification with the organization. And lastly, Quality, in which it is based on the premise that a quality way of treating individuals results in the availability of high quality products and services.

Price (n.d.) stated that the Guest Model has 6 dimensions of analysis and those are:

- HRM Strategies
- HRM Practices
- HR Outcomes
- Behavioral Outcomes
- Performance Outcomes
- Financial outcomes

Under the 6 dimension of the Guest Model each of them have specific roles. For HRM Practices have 4 roles and those are Hiring, Training, Compensation and Relations. As for HR Outcomes are Commitment, Quality and Flexibility. Behavioral Outcomes consists of Motivation, Co-operation and Organizational citizenship. And Performance Outcomes have both positive and negative side, on the positive side are Productivity, Innovation and Quality while on the negative side are Low-productivity, Absenteeism and Turnover. Lastly, Financial Outcomes that consists

of Profit and ROI.

3.1 HRM Practices

3.1.1 Hiring

The use of HRM practices for Ayesha's Farm may be able to help counter the challenges that they have now. And one of them is hiring people for their farm so they are able to cater bigger demands from their customers. As Ayesha's Farm are still in contact with their customers for maintenance of the hydroponic sets, both Aedy and Wizana will not be able to cater to all of them in a short time and hence as to why hiring employees will help with the maintenance while Aedy and Wizana could focus on other responsibilities of the business. The employee's task is to focus on the maintenance of the hydroponic sets and solving problems involving the error in the sets that cannot be solved by the machine itself. Especially when the hydroponic sets do not require a long period of time under the sun or manual labor and it even saves a lot of time than normal farming technique. This factor attracted a lot of customers that every week Ayesha's Farm have at least 2 to 3 interested buyers.

3.1.2 Training

Another HRM practices that could help Ayesha's Farm are training for Aedy and Wizana and also their future employees. Even though Aedy has attended a short course in Kuala Lumpur where he learned the several different types of farming that involves the modern technology as land become more limited and also visited other local farms for on-spot learning, they are still in the process of learning.

By having a more proper and continuous training it will provide opportunities for employees to gain more knowledge and improve their skills to become more effective in the workplace. It will

also reduce the amount of mistake and errors when doing the task as farming requires a good attention to get a good quality harvest even by using hydroponic method. Training can also prepare employees who are moving into higher jobs or roles and taking more responsibilities. For example when the business expands, Aedy and Wizana will need to learn their leadership skills as they will have more employees to maintain and supervise. Another reason is it will make the employees feel more valued and this will lead to improving their morale as well as their capabilities. By having employees feeling more valued, it is unlikely that the employee will leave Ayesha's Farm and hence reducing the employee turnover rate.

3.1.3 Relations

By having a good relations with the employees it will help in maintaining the productivity of the employee's works. As stated by Petryni (2019) workers who are invested in their job as well as other employees' well-being tend to be more productive than others who are not, leading to a higher output, revenues and profits. Having good relationships will also reduce the employee turnover as if an employee who feels like they do not know what's happening in the business may feel depressed and disconnected. As a consequence, they feel nervous and frequently explore new job options. This will be disastrous for Ayesha's Farm if Aedy and Wizana are not able to maintain their employees as most youth are more interested in office work.

3.2 HR Outcomes

3.2.1 Commitment

Another challenge for Aedy and Wizana on their farm are they have time constraints as both of them have another job that they need to focus on. In a business, having the thought of time constraint depends on the commitment that you have given to the business. Having full commitment will help Aedy and Wizana to focus and if they lack focus it can be extremely

detrimental to their business. A small problem could be a big one in a short time especially for Ayesha's Farm. The process of farming requires constant focus on the plants from seeding to harvesting and if either Aedy or Wizana did not have a constant focus during the process it will affect the quality of the harvest and may result in a loss to the business.

3.3 Behavioral Outcome

3.3.1 Motivation

Self-motivation or employee motivation is a key to success as commitment and motivation are interrelated with each other. Having an employee that have low levels of motivation the employee will work at a slower pace than normal, spending more time away from their task and possibly making themselves busy with social media such as Instagram and TikTok. This unmotivated worker will not only hinder the flow of the work but also have an effect to other employees hence holding back the business operation and meeting the company targets such as not meeting the required amount of harvest or not able to maintain the hydroponic set.

A motivated employee, on the other hand, is passionate, inspired and proud of their job. They easily execute duties, take action and try to do a good job, both for themselves and for the organization.

3.4 Performance Outcome

3.4.1 Innovation

Ayesha's Farm have a good innovation as they are able to produce the hydroponic systems since it is easier than the traditional method farming. It is easier in terms of space as traditional farming need a large area to do the harvest while hydroponic only need a small space. Another reason is the hydroponic method saves a lot of time and effort because long hours under the sun or extensive manual labor are not needed. By having an innovation Ayesha's Farm will have

room to expand and grow as they search for easier way rather than stuck in a system. With innovation a business have freedom to improve and bringing new product or service to the market.

4. ALTERNATIVE SOLUTION

4.1 Hiring

As one of the solution that was given in the case analysis were hiring new employee, it has both positive and negative outcomes for Ayesha's Farm. The pro was since the only one who works for Ayesha's Farm is Aedy and Wizana they have limited time to do the work in one day. On the other hand, when you have workers to support you, the business gets more operating hour. This means Aedy and Wizana could take on more jobs, make more cash, and expand the company to a different level.

Another pro is by having a new employee, they will bring new ideas, talent, skills, knowledge, personalities and experience. The business would be given a great deal by the new employee as they will be able to help Ayesha's Farm develop it in new ways. For example, the youth now are more knowledgeable with technology hence they could be responsible with all the newer technology of hydroponic.

However, there were also a con. Ayesha's Farm are not really experienced on recruiting new employee and this could be difficult and time consuming to recruit new employees. Aedy and Wizana would need to spend time and money promoting and interviewing applicants, and more money than the business could afford.

Another con is while hiring an employee to increase the productivity Aedy and Wizana would need to train and managing them. New employee would most likely in need of assistance hence Aedy and Wizana will need think if it's worth it or not.

4.2 Training

As for the pro on training, Aedy and Wizana will be able to improve their knowledge on hydroponic and teaches them new skills, even broadens the understanding to produce better results. Training will also gave a new idea for the business. While the con is advanced training is often pricey and as a small business Ayesha's Farm may not be able to afford.

5. RECOMMENDATION

The optimal solution for Ayesha's Farm is recruiting or hiring new employees. As having new employees could help Aedy and Wizana allocated different works and help the business gain more exposure. Even though by having more workers can be costly and time consuming but it is a great investment to the business as it help the business expand, increase productivity, new ideas, gaining more knowledge and many more.

REFERENCES

- Musa, S. F. P. D. H., Pg Hj Idris, P. S. R., & Basir, K. H. (2020). *Inspiring Agripreneurs of Brunei*. UNISSA Press, Universiti Islam Sultan Sharif Ali.
- Petryni, M. (2019). The Importance of Human Relations in the Workplace. Retrieved 9 November 2020, from <https://smallbusiness.chron.com/importance-human-relations-workplace-23061.html>
- Price, A. *Guest's model of HRM* [Ebook] (4th ed.). Retrieved from http://www.hrnguide.co.uk/introduction_to_hrm/guest-hrm.htm
- Thierry, D. (2018). *MODELIZATION OF HRM AND PERSPECTIVES FOR THE CAMEROON PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION* [Ebook] (5th ed., p. 78). Retrieved from <http://www.ijrsm.com/issues%20pdf%20file/Archive-2018/August-2018/8.pdf>